

Charting the Future of Forced Migration Research in Information Science

International Workshop at the iConference in Washington, DC United States; March 31, 2019

University of Maryland, College Park Marriott Hotel & Conference Center, Room 0101

Time	Agenda
8:30am – 9:00am	Welcome; A brief recap of the literature on forced migration in information research (Dr. Nadia Caidi, University of Toronto)
9:00am – 10:15am	Panel: The state of the research in forced migration and information from a global perspective <u>Moderator:</u> Dr. Syed Ishtiaque Ahmed (University of Toronto) <u>Panelists:</u> Dr. Faheem Hussain (Arizona State University), Dr. Juliane Stiller (Berlin School of Library and Information Science, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin), Dr. Bryan Semaan (Syracuse University), Jenny Kim (Capital Area Immigrants' Rights (CAIR) Coalition)
10:15am – 10:30am	Break and networking
10:30am – 12:00pm	Lightning talks I: Information spaces <u>Moderator:</u> Dr. Nadia Caidi (University of Toronto) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dr. Ricardo Gomez (University of Wahington Information School): "Libraries as information spaces for refugees: Participatory games and creative activities" 2. Mrs. Cansu E. Dedeoglu (University of Toronto): "Negotiating distances and boundaries: The use of ICTs in settlement service provision to newcomers in Canada" 3. Ms. Angela Mariana Schöpke (University of Michigan, School of Information): "Becoming a refugee: Understanding how we use information resources and networks to navigate changing identity"
12:00pm – 1:30pm	Lunch
1:30pm – 3:00pm	Lightning talks II: Digital environments <u>Moderator:</u> Dr. Juliane Stiller (Berlin School of Library and Information Science) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ms. Juliane Köhler (Berlin School of Library and Information Science): "Searching in a foreign country in a foreign language - Online information seeking-behavior of refugees in Germany" 2. Mr. Jamie Duncan (University of Toronto Faculty of Information): "Negotiating citizenship: Mediatized migration and the Canadian data border" 3. Dr. Hua (Helen) Wang (University at Buffalo): "Digitally-mediated environments of refugees"
3:00pm – 3:30pm	Break and networking
3:30pm – 4:45pm	Panel: Use cases and solutions for issues in forced migration <u>Moderator:</u> Dr. Violeta Trkulja (Berlin School of Library and Information Science, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin) <u>Panelists:</u> Dr. Bryce Clayton Newell (University of Kentucky), Alexandra Melinchok (University of Maryland) and Dr. Martha Kyrillidou (University of Illinois and QualityMetrics, LLC), Devendra Potnis (University of Tennessee at Knoxville)
4:45pm – 5:00pm	Wrap up; Knowledge dissemination

Organizers:

Dr. Juliane Stiller, Berlin School of Library and Information Science, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

Dr. Nadia Caidi, Faculty of Information, University Toronto, Canada

Dr. Violeta Trkulja, Berlin School of Library and Information Science, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany

Dr. Syed Ishtiaque Ahmed, Computer Science, University of Toronto, Canada